

STOP EPIDEMIC GROWTH
THROUGH LEARNING

STEP_UP | an innovative learning tool and game for pandemic preparedness

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Health emergencies of the 21st century are increasingly complex. The emergence of dangerous pathogens with epidemic and pandemic potential is rising along with the rapid globalization of travel and trade, and with major developments in technology. Emergencies and epidemics are now increasingly occurring in urban settings where, for the first time ever in human history, more than half of humanity lives. This makes it even harder to respond. Key to the new reality is the expectations of affected populations themselves. Regardless of where they live or their current socio-economic status, all countries and their citizens have a right to, and now demand, access to the best possible interventions in emergencies that increase the chances of their survival, including the highest possible levels of medical treatment and care, new medicines and vaccines. The pandemic of 2018 and the Ebola outbreak in Africa highlight the massive and widespread nature of some health emergencies that exceed the capacity of any country or agency to respond effectively. A major lesson learned from past emergencies is that even the most qualified personnel require learning and training accompanied by adequate operational support systems to equip themselves for 21st century emergencies (WHO Health Emergencies Programme, 2018).

The COVID-19 outbreak made clear that additional training is needed, not only for health care professionals but also for other target groups, such as volunteers and public authorities. It rapidly impacted every area of our lives and, in particular, created an unprecedented challenge to our health and care systems worldwide. Governments across the globe took and are still taking numerous measures to respond to the urgent care needs of those impacted, while at the same time trying to reduce the long-term impact on vulnerable people as much as possible. There are extraordinary pressures that this crisis has imposed on health and care decision-makers, but particularly on system managers and frontline staff.

Since the first COVID-19 cases appeared, countries have developed different strategies, adapted services and a wide range of innovations came up, requiring flexibility. At the same time, a wide range of innovations and willingness to adapt to these challenging times are required to all, especially to address people's continued care and support needs beyond the public health issues and crisis management.

It is not possible to consider this is a time with no consequences and that no other emergency situations will occur. The emergency state, the use of teleworking, the social distance, all implied uncovering new methods of work, understanding society's biggest fragilities and will imply changes in work and training, tools and routines that will only be clear in the next months and years.

In this process of living "remotely", by far younger generations had an easier adaptation. Already used to partially live through social media, online sources of knowledge and agile change of methods, the Millennials, and even more Generation Z, have used digital technology since a young age and can still be fully connected and maintain their training and work activities with minor deviations.

However, this is not the case of all that were born before the 1980's. If, besides age, we address adults with lower qualifications and skills, as it is the case of many workers in the social and health care sectors, the risk of being left behind due to digital illiteracy grows, thus hampering the search of reliable information.

Apart from all the innovations that are being developed and the new ways services are now being delivered, there is the need to prepare bottom-up initiatives that build-up the competences of adults in general, especially health and social care professionals, community leaders, informal caregivers and volunteers and public servants due to their privileged role as educational agents of the communities, so that these are prepared to deal with such emergency situations in the future.

After the emergency state, a collaborative leadership approach is essential, and working together as a collective, investing in a participatory citizenship, has become key.

STEP-UP developed thus a training tool for these target groups, where they are introduced to the actual impact of behaviours in the spread of a pandemic/emergency situation. There, they can learn what preventive measures exist, their impacts and the different levels of measures – individual, at work, in the family, at state level, among others. Although there is plenty of information available online, it is difficult to know which one is reliable. Also, there is the need to prepare the right training methods to approach the care sector as community educational agents, in an adequate and engaging way.

The core of this tool is an educational game, but it can also be used as a recreational game for the common public.

It intends to go on the contrary direction of existing games, (e.g. Plague inc., which objective is to create a plague that infects the whole world. In STEP-UP, instead of searching for chaos, the players intend to do the exact opposite - play with the aim to stop a pandemic from spreading.

In the game, several measures are displayed as optional in different formats and settings, and the player needs to learn about them in order to be able to choose those that would help to impede the virus spread without damaging the economy or causing societal anger. This also helps learners to better understand and follow governmental measures (which they not always do in restriction situations) and to set aside true facts from myths and fake news.

STEP-UP is first aiming at adults that work or are interested in social care, community work, healthcare and public servants, with a fully devised training toolkit, which includes the game, training materials and guidance. However, for a wider exploitation and in order to increase informal education, the game is usable by any citizen and will therefore have a larger aim in adult training, especially of those with lower skills and qualifications.

Besides the gaming tool and the complete training toolkit, a manual on social and policy interventions is delivered, offering targeted guidelines and insights on early detection, preventive measures, health and social care interventions and policy measures for EU countries.

The three main results of the project are further presented in detail:

STEP UP educational platform and game

To provide a new, innovative and appealing training instrument to address the challenges of epidemics or pandemics, the STEP UP project developed an interactive learning platform, where learners can learn to tackle and prevent health emergencies. Its core is an interactive 2D learning game (IO1), but the platform also offers additional training material for adult learners, such as a Trainer Toolkit and Workshop Curriculum with handouts, templates for rewards and certificates (IO3) and a Manual on Social and Policy Interventions (IO2). All outcomes are available in Portuguese, Dutch, English, Spanish, German, and Croatian, both online and in the Erasmus Results Platform.

STEP UP's educational game (also open to recreational usage) aims to train adult learners on the actual impact of behaviours in the spread of a pandemic / health threatening emergency situation. The main target groups are community leaders, social care professionals, municipality workers and volunteers associations, especially in their role as educational agents of the broader community, focusing on adults with lower skills and qualifications. The game includes preventive measures, impacts and the different levels of measures that individuals, organisations and authorities could take.

The game starts in the STEP_UP island where the player hears that the first COVID19 case has been detected. It is then invited to meet 5 different characters. The player will support the work of 5 available characters from different areas of society and play through 25 scenes: a volunteer, a policy maker / politician, a caregiver / auxiliary worker in a care home for older adults, a public health / epidemiologist, a primary care centre manager.

It can be played in chronological order, from the outbreak to the end of a pandemic, from the single perspective of a specific character and area, or else the player can choose a wild card, which means that the game will select the scenes and events will occur randomly.

The player is confronted with typical situations during a pandemic in STEP_UP Island and offered insights on early detection, preventive measures (such as washing hands and avoid contacts), healthcare measures (precautious measures for professionals, vaccines, treatments, intensive care), public authority measures (isolation, lockdown, communication), and potential exit strategies. He will also learn about how different choices have different ethical concerns and societal implications.

The interactions within the game are framed by a story with a pending problem at the beginning, its development during the play and resolutions to the problem upon completion of the game. Learning aids include puzzles or quizzes and several mini-games that will provide a gamification asset and increase motivation during the game.

This will support the player's evaluation of the situation and the decisions he or she may take. In order to increase the competence of the player, in some of the scenes the player will be asked to choose between alternative forms of behaviour, such as a more or less active role in the resolution. After the interaction, the player will receive feedback from the character in the game or immediately sees the consequences of choices.

It is a visual novel/ point and click: the player will react to the events of the game through a point-and-click interface. It is designed to be played on a computer and mouse. Although it can respond in mobile phones and small tablets, it was not developed to that purpose and can thus be less than optimal in such devices. There is an optional registration and login for players who want to save progress. Others can play freely, and no data is requested. A progress dashboard is made available through the game where the player can see their progress. This is printable as a visual progress report that can be shared in social media to stimulate others to also play.

In the opening of the game the player can go to “It is my first time in STEP_UP, please show me around!” and visit the areas About the game, Meet the characters and Learning objectives or select “I am already a STEP_UPper. Take me directly to play!”

The objective is to take the best decisions for each event. The performance of the player is visible on the screen through the “COVID-9 spread control bar” and the “Society wellbeing graph”. These bars have colours for the player to understand how is the level of social wellbeing and whether the island is free of the virus.

In addition to the points, the rewards for the mini-games will be given in diamonds. These diamonds can be used to buy items every 5 scenes (chronological mode), or to buy items at the end of the game. In what concerns the scoring system, every 5 scenes the player is taken to a shop to buy different measures that will help them to enhance the game results, with cheaper and more expensive options, depending on available diamonds. At the end of the game, a list of images is available to send/download to friends and to invite them to also play the game. Besides the progress report validating the playing, there are also templates for certificates and proofs of participation available in the Trainer Area if the game is used in workshop settings.

One innovative aspect of this IO is that the characters, environments and scenes, measures etc. were developed in co-design workshops, where the target group of learners were invited to co-create the appropriate features of the learning game, supported also by additional desk research when needed. The script was then co-written by the consortium partners, each devoted to one character and peer-reviewed by all to ensure coherence and attention to cultural differences. The game was tested in the LTTA and MEs and all feedback incorporated iteratively towards the final version.

Social and Policy Interventions Manual

The Social and Policy Interventions Manual is meant for and co-created by (policy) advisors in municipalities, public health authorities, social and healthcare and volunteers’ organisations. The main aim of the manual is to provide an easily accessible and useful manual to advisors with social and policy interventions examples, lessons learned and successes for the different stages of health emergencies.

To prepare the building of the game (IO1), IO2 began with an extensive review of relevant and accurate materials on the COVID19 pandemic and other relevant epidemic or pandemic outbreaks, as well as societal measures to deal with emergency situations. These materials were used also as background information to develop the Manual (O2), that offers target-group oriented guidelines and insights on the following measures areas: communication, social

healthcare and political. The manual was completed with real-life oriented user stories, good practices and lessons learned.

The first usage of the materials collected was at the development of a Virtual Library. It is hosted in the project online platform and includes more than 500 measures to be consulted, that were collected and duly categorised by all partners under the leadership of AFE and SHINE. Although this was not initially foreseen, the consortium decided to enhance the interactivity of this tool by releasing a permanent international call to submit measures and best practices that were (and will be) integrated into this online repository, through an online survey available in the website. The entries were periodically reviewed and published by the partners and will now be under SHINE management that is committed to keep it up to date, even after the project end.

Based on the desk research and consultation workshops, five Thematic Reports were also developed 1) early detection, 2) preventive measures, 3) health and social care interventions, 4) policy measures and 5) communication. Each partner was responsible for one theme and performed this together with the target groups and these reports were further used to develop the Manual.

The work led by AFE to prepare the Manual, led to the development of a survey that collected feedback from 133 participants to receive contextual opinions and feedback on measures from multiple countries. The work in IO2 continued with the writing of the manual itself, peer reviews and second opinion check with interviewees, and concluded with the translation and dissemination of the Manual.

More in detail, the social and policy interventions manual provides guidelines to specific questions, through the following content:

1. Introduction on epidemic and pandemic virus outbreaks: short introduction on the main features and consequences of known virus outbreaks, with useful links.

2. Early detection: which systems are available in the partner countries and globally to detect a health emergency virus outbreak, how useful are these, what is the relevancy? Learning from early detection successes and failures, such as vaccines against Bird's Flu, the regional/national character of SARS and MERS and Ebola. The, for many people, unexpected transfer of COVID-19 to the rest of the world, where the first patient was detected in Wuhan and the lack of preparation on it. As regards social and policy interventions the following questions arise: What can public authorities, healthcare providers and volunteers best do to evaluate outbreaks with the help of experts, how to communicate with professionals and the general public, which preparation measures are suitable and feasible? Are vaccines available and how to foster their rapid development?

3. Early outbreak of the health emergency: patient zero has been identified on the territory. Which measures should public authorities, health and social care providers and volunteers take to isolate the spreading of affections, contact research, technology (apps) to use, which privacy issues do measures contain, which preparation measures of social care facilities is needed? Is an immediate lockdown needed? Which are the effects on the economy? How to communicate with the other professionals involved in social and health care and the general public? More important, how to communicate with social care clients - older adults and their relatives, vulnerable people, children, parents and empowered families, troubled youngsters?

4. The outbreak is epidemic or pandemic: the spreading of the virus is going fast and many more individuals are affected. Some of them need to be hospitalized or being transferred to intensive care facilities. How to prepare social care organisations: medicines, personnel, equipment, beds. Which measures should be taken to stop the further spreading? How long should the measures stand? How to communicate with experts, professionals and the general public? What considerations should be considered in terms of: gender - can be analysed in Corona's incidence and on the severity of the symptoms but also in terms of work-life balance, due to the restriction to stay at home and the division of daily tasks in couples; inequalities - not only for access to health and care but also socio-economic; ethics - reflections on choices.

5. Exit strategy or open-up again: the epidemic or pandemic successfully has been stopped, but which measures are needed to return to 'back to normal'? Can we return to 'back to normal' or do we have to change our ways of living? In the COVID-19 crisis, solutions are offered in technologies (China: allowed to travel if you have a green colour; orange: awareness if you were near a corona positive person and red: 2 weeks of isolation) or in thinking in terms of a 1.5 meter economy for shops, restaurants, offices, transport etc. Which additional measures are needed? How to communicate with experts, professionals and the general public?

The Manual's content is taken to the platform and game (IO1) but also leveraged for IO3, the Trainer Toolkit.

Trainer Toolkit and Workshop Curriculum

The STEP-UP game and the guidelines on potential measures in a pandemic situation can also be embedded in a structured workshop. Learning concepts that are tailored to new digital opportunities such as STEP_UP can increase the attractiveness of non-formal educational offers in general. However, adult educators must be able to deal with the new media, and many are not familiar with a digital work environment. The project also contributes to close this gap. The Trainer Toolkit and Workshop Curriculum offers a user-friendly approach to working with the STEP-UP game thus making use of digital media in adult education.

Besides using the game and accompanying materials on the impact of behaviour in pandemic situations, workshops offer the opportunity for more intensive reflections and discussions, as experienced in the LTTA and MEs. It serves to refer to background information and discuss contents of the game as well as the broad range of preventive measures that contribute to a deceleration of infections. Here the participants have the opportunity to share ideas and intervention approaches with other workshop participants.

It covers the following areas:

1. Personal approach / low-threshold access to the topic: The participants bring in their own knowledge and experiences on the impacts of individual behaviours and preventive measures in the different spheres of life. Playing the game is part of the workshop and used as a low-threshold approach to raising awareness.

2. Analysis: Problems of inappropriate behaviours of certain target groups - both in their families and in public spaces - are then discussed at structural level. Reports on experiences from the workshops for designing the game will also be used here.

3. Learning about dealing with conflicts and potential solutions: The range of measures to preventive measures, be it by individual, technical or political interventions, are presented and discussed in terms of personal and structural prerequisites. The results from IO2 are used to illustrate the different options, and conflicting interests are discussed.

4. Positive exit: Finally, options for action are developed and tried out on the basis of own incidents and experiences. Where appropriate, exercises like role-plays are performed.

The Trainer Toolkit is composed of the following sections:

1. Background information on the topic.

2. The workshop curriculum contains in-depths information on conducting the workshop sections and includes learning objectives, time schedules, didactic methods and means (pictures, quotations, videos), handouts, a PPT template, suggestions for the learning environment, the evaluation of the training and recommendations of good practice.

3. Further awareness is given to potential needs of adult educators who are not familiar with applying digital media in their trainings.

4. The Toolkit further contains a section on validation and certification as learning outcomes that are acquired in non-formal and informal settings also need to be validated and recognized. Different options based on examples of good practice – ranging from the game’s progress report to the issuing a certificate with training topics are described and illustrated by templates ready for use. A special focus was given on potential national and European instruments to make the learning progress visible and valid for future employers, scholarships, etc.

The Trainer Toolkit and Workshop Curriculum treats the workshop implementation and the application of digital media from a European and holistic perspective. As all partners are involved in the elaboration of the trainer manual, its transferability to other national contexts was ensured. Embedding the STEP-UP game in a workshop structure constitutes an attractive offer for civic education providers and increase their chances to address also persons who would regularly prefer informal learning experiences. By not taking the digital working skills of adult educators for granted but providing those in need of support with additional aids, the Toolkit will also contribute to their professional further development.

The Trainer Toolkit is available as a sole document integrating all parts, but it is also published in separate items in the Trainer Area for easiness of use of facilitators and other adult educators.

All information available in <https://stepupgame.eu>